

***PREDICTING FAILURE IN FIBRE COMPOSITES:
FINAL CHAPTER OF THE WORLD-WIDE FAILURE
EXERCISE***

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SUMMARY

The ‘World-Wide Failure Exercise’ (WWFE) was launched by the authors, some 10 years ago, to establish the status of currently available theoretical methods for predicting material failure in fibre reinforced polymer composites materials. The ‘exercise’ has encompassed 19 distinct theoretical approaches, from groups in 6 countries, utilising 15 test cases defined by the organisers and is now virtually complete. This paper is the last in a sequence, starting at ICCM-10, aimed at alerting the community to the breadth of knowledge that has emerged.

In the paper the authors have focussed on the lessons learned on two of the key issues that are fundamental to the credibility of any failure theory. These are (a) how well do the theories predict the strength of unidirectional laminates, over a range of stress states, and (b) how well do the theories predict the point at which initial failure is observed in multi-directional laminates, over a range of stress states. The two issues were explored by comparing the theoretical predictions with experimental data selected from the 15 test cases utilised in the ‘exercise’.

Predicting the strength of a unidirectional laminate under combined loading proved to be very discriminatory examination of the various theories. Certain theories produced a good correlation with experimental results, thereby passing the first test to increase confidence in their value as a design tool. However others give an uncomfortably large deviation from the experimental observations, thereby shedding doubt on their usefulness as a design aid.

Predicting the point of onset of initial failure in multi-directional laminates proved to be even more of a challenge for the theories, and something of a challenge for the experimentalists. Large divergences were observed both when comparing the theoretical predictions with each other, and when comparing the theoretical predictions with the experimental observations. This serves to highlight important philosophical differences between a designer and a theoretician over the definition of what constitutes ‘initial failure’ of a laminated structure.

KEYWORDS: failure, laminates, biaxial, stresses, strength.

1. INTRODUCTION

At the start of the ‘exercise’, the authors (referred to, hereafter, as the organisers) had three principal goals in mind. These were (Ref [1]), to:-

- Establish the current level of maturity of theories for predicting the failure response of fibre reinforced plastic (FRP) laminates
- Close the knowledge gap between theoreticians and design practitioners in this field
- Stimulate the composites community into providing design engineers with more robust and accurate failure prediction methods, and the confidence to use them.

Much thought was given as to how to configure the ‘exercise’ to achieve those goals and the organisers

consulted widely to evolve a truly objective methodology. A critical element was to ensure that the theories were described and the theoretical predictions made *in advance* of any participant receiving the experimental results, thus ensuring that a true, ‘blind’, prediction had been made. As a result of these considerations (Ref [1]), the main body of the exercise was run in two parts identified as ‘Part A’ and ‘Part B’. Part A, published in 1998 (Ref [2]), was devoted to providing full details of the theories together with predictions (made by the originators of the theories) for a common set of test cases, defined by the organisers. Part B, published in 2002 (Ref [3]), focused on a comparison of the theoretical predictions made in Part A against the experimental results (provided by the organisers), whilst allowing the participants to introduce improvements to their own theory, and to have a general ‘right to reply’. An additional element of the exercise, Part C (submitted for publication in 2003, Ref [4]), was undertaken to capture a ‘new wave’ of theories which have emerged since the start of the main body of the exercise. Five additional groups have taken part, each submitting two papers, to mirror Parts A and B utilised in the main body. Great care was taken over the timing of information release to the participants in Part C to ensure that the ‘blind’ prediction principals were maintained (see Ref [5]).

The present paper concentrates on the recent progress and lessons learned from Parts A, B and C of the exercise. In particular, attempts are made to illustrate the capability of all 19 different theoretical methodologies, employed by their originators, to predict the biaxial failure envelopes for unidirectional laminae under combined direct and shear stresses and the initial failure envelopes for two multi-directional laminates subjected to a range of biaxial loads. The results are compared and contrasted with available experimental evidence. Certain factors affecting the prediction of initial failure in laminates are discussed.

2. PARTICIPANTS AND PREDICTIVE METHODS USED

Comprehensive descriptions of the theoretical methodologies used by the participants (normally the originators of the theories) in the ‘exercise’ are provided in Refs[2,4]. Table 1 summarises the participants (first column), the institutions they represent (second column) and a simplified reference identifier used in later figures in this paper (third column). A distinction is made between the original participants in Part A and Part B, and the new participants in Part C of the failure exercise.

In general, each methodology used is unique in its formulation, its detection of failure and its post failure treatment. However, in some instances, there were similarities in the way failure is predicted at certain levels. As an example, Bogetti et al, Ref[4] and Hart-Smith(2), Ref[2], both used maximum strain theory to determine failure on a lamina level. However, the former allowed for shear non-linearity and progressive failure behaviour whereas the latter did not.

Table 1 A summary of participants and approaches represented in the WWFE

Contributor(s)	Organisation	Theory designation
Chamis C C, Gotsis P K and Minnetyan L	NASA Lewis, Cleveland, USA	Chamis (1) [□] Chamis (2) [□]
Hart-Smith L J	Boeing, USA	Hart-Smith(1) [□]
Hart-Smith L J	Boeing, USA	Hart-Smith(2) [□]
Eckold G C	AEA Technology, UK	Eckold [□]
Edge E C	British Aerospace, Military Aircraft Division, Warton, UK	Edge [□]
McCartney L N	National Physical Laboratory, London, UK	McCartney [□]
Puck A and Schürmann H	Technische Hochschule, Darmstadt, Germany	Puck [□]
Wolfe W E and Butalia T S	Department of Civil Engineering, Ohio State University, Ohio, USA	Wolfe [□]
Sun C T and Tao J X	Purdue University School of Aeronautics &	Sun(L) [□]

	Astronautics, West Lafayette, Indiana, USA.	Sun(NL) [□]
Zinoviev P, Grigoriev S V, Labedeva O V and Tairova L R	Institute of Composite Technologies, Orevo, Moskovskaya, Russia.	Zinoviev [□]
Tsai S W and Liu K-S	Aeronautics and Astronautics Department, Stanford University, California, USA.	Tsai [□]
Rotem A	Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Technion-Israel Institute of Technology, Haifa, Israel.	Rotem [□]
Cuntze R and A Freund	MAN Technologies, Germany	Cuntze *
Bogetti T, C Hoppel, V Harik, J Newill and B Burns	U.S. Army Research Laboratory, AMSRL-WM-MB, Aberdeen Proving Ground, MD 21005	Bogetti *
Mayes S J and A C Hansen	US Naval Surface Warfare Center, West Bethesda, MD, and Alfred University	Mayes *
Z-M Huang	Department of Engineering Mechanics, Tongji University, Shanghai, China	Huang *
Hart-Smith L J	Boeing, USA	Hart-Smith(3) *

[□] Parts A & B * Part C

3. TEST CASES PROVIDED

In total, 15 Test cases were provided in the ‘exercise’. These are summarised in Table 2, though the reader should note that a full definition of each, as supplied to the participants, can be found at Ref [6]. The present paper focuses on Test Cases 1, 3 and the initial failure stresses in test cases 6, 9 and 13. The matching experimental results, exactly as supplied to the participants, are described fully in Ref [7].

Table 2 Summary of the laminates and loading (test) cases

Test Case	Laminate Lay-up	Material	Description of Required Prediction
1*	0°	E-glass/LY556	σ_y versus τ_{xy} envelope
2*	0°	T300/BSL914C	σ_x versus τ_{xy} envelope
3*	0°	E-glass/MY750	σ_y versus σ_x envelope
4*	(±30°/90°)	E-glass/LY556	σ_y versus σ_x envelope
5*	(±30°/90°)	E-glass/LY556	σ_x versus τ_{xy} envelope
6*	(0°/±45°/90°)	AS4/3501-6	σ_y versus σ_x envelope
7	(0°/±45°/90°)	AS4/3501-6	Stress-strain curves for $\sigma_y : \sigma_x = 1 : 0$
8	(0°/±45°/90°)	AS4/3501-6	Stress-strain curves for $\sigma_y : \sigma_x = 2 : 1$
9*	±55°	E-glass/MY750	σ_y versus σ_x envelope
10	±55°	E-glass/MY750	Stress-strain curves for $\sigma_y : \sigma_x = 1 : 0$
11	±55°	E-glass/MY750	Stress-strain curves for $\sigma_y : \sigma_x = 2 : 1$
12	(0°/90°)	E-glass/MY750	Stress-strain curves for $\sigma_y : \sigma_x = 0 : 1$
13	±45°	E-glass/MY750	Stress-strain curves for $\sigma_y : \sigma_x = 1 : 1$
14	±45°	E-glass/MY750	Stress-strain curves for $\sigma_y : \sigma_x = 1 : -1$
15**	±55°	E-glass/MY750	Deformed shape of a tube under pressure

* Biaxial failure stress envelopes under a wide range of biaxial stress ratios

** This Case was provided only in Part B whereas the rest was provided in Part A.

4. COMPARISON BETWEEN THEORY AND EXPERIMENTS

4.1 Test Case 1: Failure envelopes for the 0° E-glass/LY556 epoxy lamina under combined transverse direct and shear loads

Figure 1 shows a comparison between the prediction of a number of failure theories and experimental data for hoop wound glass/epoxy tubes tested under combined transverse (perpendicular to fibre direction) tension/compression and torsion

loading. Two main features can be seen in the experimental data (a) the decrease in the shear strength due to application of tension stress and (b) the enhancement in the shear strength due to the application of moderate compressive stress. These two features have been captured satisfactorily by some theories, for example, Puck, Tsai and Cuntze but not by others. Three of the predictions, Hart-Smith3, Eckold and the distinctive curve produced by Huang fail to pass through the key point of the uniaxial transverse tensile strength value for the lamina (which was provided by the organisers to participants in their test case definition packs, Ref[6]).

4.2 Test Case 3: Failure envelopes for the 0° E-glass/MY750 epoxy lamina under biaxial loads

The behaviour of a unidirectional (UD) lamina under combined longitudinal and transverse loading is shown in Fig 2. The experimental data were obtained using hoop filament wound tubes loaded under a combination of internal pressure and axial compression. The data were rather sparse, lying primarily in the longitudinal tension, transverse compression quadrant. The reader should note that reliable experimental biaxial data is particularly hard to obtain in the other quadrants. The originators of this data set (Ref[7]) took a pragmatic view as to what could be readily obtained, hence the

Fig 1 Comparison between test data and theory for 0° E-glass/LY556 laminate under biaxial loads, (σ_y versus τ_{xy}), Test Case 1

Fig 2 Failure envelopes for the 0° E-glass/epoxy lamina under biaxial loads, (σ_x versus σ_y). (Test Case 3)

sparseness in the data set. The theories (those of Tsai, Chamis and Bogetti) involve

Some of the predictions show features that (a) the ‘notable’ increase in the biaxial tension predicted by Hart-Smith (2), Bogetti (2), and Mayes (2); (b) the large increase in the biaxial stress compression predicted by Tsai, Hart-Smith (1), and Wolfe (1); (c) the inability to predict one or more experimental results.

The sparseness in the experimental data can still identify those theories that disagree with the experimental results.

Fig 4 Biaxial envelopes for the $\pm 55^\circ$ E-glass/MY750 laminate under biaxial loads, (σ_y versus σ_x), (Test Case 9).

Graphs showing the predicted initial failure envelopes for this quasi-isotropic laminate are presented in Fig 3, together with experimental initial failure results for some combinations of biaxial tension. The experimental results correspond to the first observed change in slope of the stress-strain curves derived from the tests, Ref[7]. There is a very wide range of predicted initial failure stresses (see discussion Section 5, below) and all lie below the experimental results.

4.4 Failure envelopes for the $(\pm 55^\circ)$, E-glass/MY750 epoxy laminate under biaxial loads, (σ_y versus σ_x), (Test Case 9)

Only the initial failure prediction will be described here. The experimental results were obtained from testing tubes without a liner, under combination of either internal or external pressure and either axial tension or compression. Initial failure was defined as the point at which onset of leakage of fluid through the tube wall could be observed. Fig 4 shows the correlation between the initial failure predictions and the

leakage test data.

In general, almost all of the theoretical predictions were very conservative (i.e under-predicted the leakage strength). In certain instances (see for instance Chamis's theory, at hoop to axial stress ratio=3:1) the degree of conservatism reached nearly 10 fold. A few theories, particularly Huang, produced over-optimistic predictions for small portions of the failure envelope. It should be noted that Huang used data for the lamina properties that were higher than those used by the rest of the authors and those provided by the organisers in Ref[6].

4.5 Stress-strain curves for a $\pm 45^\circ$, E-glass/MY750 epoxy laminate under equal biaxial tensile loads, ($\sigma_y : \sigma_x = 1 : 1$) (Test Case 13)

Only the initial failure prediction will be described here. The experimental results were derived from tests on a lined $\pm 45^\circ$ filament wound tube loaded under combined internal pressure and axial tension to produce equal biaxial tension stresses (SR=1:1). Initial failure was defined as the point at which the first micro-cracking could be observed in the tube. Secondary failure was observed at a significantly higher loading level and this was defined by the onset of leakage of fluid through the tube wall.

Fig 5 portrays the performance of all of the theories in predicting the micro-cracking failure, in histogram format. Two horizontal lines are drawn, one passing through a vertical value of 1 and another through a vertical value of 4.2. The former represents matrix micro cracking and the latter gives an indication on how far the leakage stress is away from the matrix cracking stress.

The majority of the theoretical predictions lie between the stress levels at which first and secondary modes

Fig 5 A bar chart showing the initial failure prediction for $\pm 45^\circ$ E-glass/MY750 laminate tested under a stress ratio $\sigma_y : \sigma_x = 1:1$, (Test Case 13).

of failure (as defined above) were observed. The figure shows that most of the theories were non-conservative in their predictions of stress level for initial failure, by a factor of up to 2.5, in comparison with the observed initial micro-cracking stress. In contrast, all of the theories were conservative in their predictions of stress level for initial failure, by a factor of up to 4.5, when compared with the observed leakage stress.. Thus, none of the theories was capable of predicting the leakage failure, which constitutes a significant limitation in the current failure theories.

5. DISCUSSION OF INITIAL FAILURE PREDICTION

A wide range of initial failure predictions was produced by the various theories in Part A of the failure exercise and that range was further increased by the contributions to Part C.

There are a number of issues affecting the prediction of initial failure stresses including the type of failure criterion used, the type of analysis (linear or nonlinear), in-situ effects and so on. One extra important contributory factor to the variation in initial failure results, at the multi-directional laminate level, was the difference between predicted residual stresses arising from cooling of the laminates after curing. The contributors were all given the same information about the curing cycle and the stress free temperature (Ref[6]). No information was provided about the moisture content and the participants requested none. The contributors made a variety of assumptions. Some ignored residual stresses altogether whilst others made full allowance for the effects of cooling after curing and ignored moisture content, which was the organiser's intention. Others assumed arbitrary moisture contents; Tsai for example assumed moisture contents that cancelled out the effects of temperature change. The effect of these different assumptions was far from negligible. Chamis et al [2] demonstrated dramatic differences between the initial failure strengths predicted for the ($0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ$) quasi-isotropic laminate loaded under biaxial tension (Test Case 6) depending on whether residual stresses were ignored or taken into account. When residual stresses were taken into consideration in multi directional laminates, contributors usually employed conventional (ie linear-elastic) laminate theory to allow for the effects of different thermal expansion coefficients of laminae in directions parallel and perpendicular to the fibres. Only Huang Ref [4] appears to have attempted to allow for different contractions at a constituent level, i.e. between resin and fibres.

Another important factor is that an event perceived as the first significant change in behaviour in an experiment may not be the same as the event that is predicted as the first failure in a theoretical analysis. For example, whilst most theories predicted initial failure as the onset of cracking, in the quasi-isotropic carbon-fibre/epoxy laminate experiments (Test Case 6 -Fig 3) initial failure was taken by the originators of the experimental results and hence by the organisers as the first detectable change in stiffness of the laminate.

In the E glass/epoxy angle-ply tubes tested under internal pressure (Test Case13, Fig 4) the first observed failure was leakage of fluid through the tube wall and it was widely assumed that this would correspond with the initial failure predicted by theory, which is usually associated with ply cracking due to tensile stresses perpendicular to the fibres. In both cases it is possible that some undetected cracking had occurred before any significant, change in stiffness or leakage was detectable. Un-pigmented Glass/epoxy composites are semi-transparent and careful observations under controlled illumination may allow observation of damage development during loading. The results for one such test, the $\pm 45^\circ$ E-glass/epoxy tube under equal biaxial tension (Test Case 13), are shown in Fig.5, which confirms that in this case resin cracking was observed well before leakage occurred.

6. ASSESSMENT OF THE OVERALL AGREEMENT BETWEEN THEORETICAL PREDICTIONS AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In order to highlight the degree of agreement between the theoretical predictions and the whole range of available test data, an assessment was made in Refs [4,8], using detailed quantitative and qualitative procedures. The procedures are based upon a systematic comparison of the predicted strengths and deformations against the experimental values for (a) biaxial strength of unidirectional laminae, (b) 'initial' biaxial strengths of multi-directional laminates, (c) 'final' strengths of multi-directional laminates, (d) deformation (stress / strain curves) of multi-directional laminates, and (e) ability to predict the general trends observed in the test data

The procedures were designed to expose areas where the failure theories are believed to be relatively mature in their predictive capability and also, importantly, areas where the current understanding of failure is lacking and where the theoretical predictions differed from the test data by a significant margin. This information has been translated into a form which will help design engineers to identify the likely level of accuracy to be expected from a theoretical prediction in a given situation and provide guidance on which theory to employ, Refs [4,8].

As far as the initial failure prediction is concerned, the assessment indicated that :-

- (a) Where highly accurate predictions are required (ie within $\pm 10\%$), the best of the current theories could only achieve this in 15% of the test features..
- (b) Where a broad accuracy level is required (ie within $\pm 50\%$) the best of the current theories demonstrated that level in 80% of the test features.

7. CONCLUSIONS

A number of conclusions may be drawn from the work discussed here:-

On the prediction of UD lamina behaviour

- No two theories employed in the failure exercise gave identical prediction of all the UD lamina biaxial failure envelopes.
- A number of theories (e.g.Puck, Cuntze and Tsai) gave reasonably accurate predictions of the available experimental data on the strength of the UD laminae under combined loading.
- The present test data were not sufficient to confirm the 'notable' increase in the biaxial failure stresses under longitudinal and transverse tension predicted by Hart-Smith, Bogetti and Wolfe's theories and that under longitudinal and transverse compression predicted by Tsai, Hart-Smith and Bogetti's theories.

On the prediction of initial failure

- The prediction and interpretation of the significance of initial failure was one area where difficulties were encountered in this exercise. The correlation between available test data and most of the theoretical predictions was generally poor
- There was a lack of consensus on how to deal with residual stresses arising from curing.
- The prediction of the onset of cracking was not sufficient to predict leakage failure of pressurised containers
- Further experimental work is required to provide information on the onset and development of cracking in laminates and on its practical significance or otherwise in practical situations of interest to designers

On the overall results of the exercise

- The readers are recommended to consult with Refs[2-4] for a fuller appreciation of the complete set of lessons learnt from this exercise.
- The overall objectives of the exercise have been achieved

- Weaknesses and strengths of the various theories and experimental results have been revealed
- Areas for future development have been identified and some of the participants have already made improvements to their theories.

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